

Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of Transition Metals. Part (III) : Complexes of Copper(II) Succinate with Aniline, Toluidines and Pyridine

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Five complexes of Copper(II) succinate of the type CuSucc. (am)_2 , where 'am' stands for any of the above mentioned amines have been prepared in methanol solutions and crystallised. The complexes have been characterised and assigned above formula on the basis of elemental analysis and molar conductance data. The co-ordination of succinate ion and amines to Copper(II) is indicated by the infrared spectra while magnetic and spectroscopic measurements indicates nearly planer geometries for the complexes.

In the past one decade the interest of transition metal complexes is shifting from the use of inorganic anions to organic anions and a large number of complexes of organic anions such as phthalimide, succinimide, oxalate, formate, benzoate and phthalate with first transition series metals have been reported from this laboratory¹⁻¹¹. We have now undertaken the study of transition metal succinates and their complexes. The succinate ion, like phthalate ion, contains two COO^- groups and is thus expected to have as a bidentate ligand itself, occupying any two adjacent positions in the coordination geometry of Copper(II). The amines are thus left with other two available positions. The present paper records the preparation of five complexes of Copper(II) succinate with amines as aniline; *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidines and pyridine, which have been fully characterised by using conductivity, infrared, magnetic and electronic spectral data.

Experimental

Copper(II) succinate was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of Sodium(I) succinate to Copper(II) sulphate. The blue compound was filtered, washed repeatedly with water, dried and analysed and its formula worked out to be $\text{Cu Succinate} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

This was suspended in methanol, a little more than the calculated quantity of amine was added and the solution refluxed for few hours. The complex was crystallised out from this solution, analysed and the results of analysis are given below :

1. *Succinate bi(aniline) Copper(II)* : $\text{Cu} = 17.82\%$; $\text{C} = 50.90\%$; $\text{H} = 5.02\%$; $\text{N} = 7.23\%$; $\text{CuC}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires $\text{Cu} = 17.38\%$; $\text{C} = 51.95\%$; $\text{H} = 4.92\%$ and $\text{N} = 7.66\%$.

Colour – Green

2. *Succinate bi(o-toluidine) Copper(II)* : $\text{Cu} = 16.40\%$; $\text{C} = 54.80\%$; $\text{H} = 6.02\%$; $\text{N} = 8.10\%$;

$\text{CuC}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires $\text{Cu} = 16.14\%$; $\text{C} = 54.91\%$; $\text{H} = 5.59\%$ and $\text{N} = 7.11\%$.

Colour – Greenish blue

3. *Succinate bi(m-toluidine) Copper(II)* : $\text{Cu} = 16.82\%$; $\text{C} = 54.28\%$; $\text{H} = 5.72\%$; $\text{N} = 7.65\%$; $\text{CuC}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires $\text{Cu} = 16.14\%$; $\text{C} = 54.91\%$; $\text{H} = 5.59\%$; $\text{N} = 7.11\%$.

Colour – Greenish blue

4. *Succinate bi(p-toluidine) Copper(II)* : $\text{Cu} = 16.82\%$; $\text{C} = 54.08\%$; $\text{H} = 5.98\%$; $\text{N} = 6.89\%$; $\text{CuC}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires $\text{Cu} = 16.14\%$; $\text{C} = 54.91\%$; $\text{H} = 5.59\%$; $\text{N} = 7.11\%$.

Colour – Olive green

5. *Succinate bi(pyridine) Copper(II)* : $\text{Cu} = 18.50\%$; $\text{C} = 49.28\%$; $\text{H} = 4.94\%$; $\text{N} = 8.69\%$; $\text{CuC}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ requires $\text{Cu} = 18.82\%$; $\text{C} = 49.78\%$; $\text{H} = 4.14\%$ and $\text{N} = 8.29\%$.

Colour – Light blue

Conductivities were measured in nitrobenzene at a concentration of $10^{-3}M$ on a Philips PR 9500 magic eye type instrument and values given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complexes	Molar conductance in mhos	μ_{eff} in B.M.	λ_{max}	Frequency in cm^{-1}	Dq in cm^{-1}
$\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4(\text{aniline})_2$	1.5	1.845	696	14,370	1437
$\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4(o\text{-tolu.})_2$	2.0	1.855	705	14,170	1417
$\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4(m\text{-tolu.})_2$	0.9	1.871	715	13,582	1358
$\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4(p\text{-tolu.})_2$	0.8	1.886	698	14,320	1432
$\text{CuC}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_4(\text{Py})_2$	1.0	1.921	660	15,310	1531

I. R. and electronic spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 in a region 400-400 cm^{-1} and on VSU 12 spectrometer in the form of solid sample respectively. The magnetic measurements were made on powdered samples by using Gouy's method and these values are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The percentage of constituents elements show the molecular formula to be Cu Succ(am)_2 while the molar conductance values are in the usual range of nonelectrolytic complexes. It thus appears that the succinate ion is also co-ordinated along with the amines and the formulae are $[\text{Cu. Succ(am)}_2]$. Further evidences for the co-ordination of ligands is obtained from the infrared spectra as discussed below.

I. R. spectra of succinate ion :

The succinate ion belongs to high symmetry point group C_{2v} and due to the presence of a center of symmetry passing through the ion, these absorption bands which are symmetric across the center are forbidden in the I. R. spectra. The CH_2 bending and COO^- symmetric stretchings which are observed in the form of strong peak at 1438 cm^{-1} and a shoulder on its longer wave length side in Sodium(I) succinate are shifted to lower wave lengths in co-ordination. Two or even three bands are observed in the complexes with medium to strong intensity in the range $1420\text{-}1360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ thus undergiving a negative shift of about 60 cm^{-1} . This is due to the co-ordination of the ion^{12,13}. The sharp bands at 1226 cm^{-1} and 1176 cm^{-1} of sodium succinate are assigned to CH_2 Wagging and twisting frequencies respectively. In complexes both these are split and shifted to higher frequencies by about 100 cm^{-1} , and appears at 1300 & 1275 cm^{-1} which confirms the co-ordination, as bands in the above range are characteristic of co-ordinated carboxylate ion¹⁴. In addition to these each complex also shows a medium to strong band at 805 cm^{-1} attributable to CH_2 rocking, which is due to the trans configuration of the carbon chains.

I. R. of aniline and toluidine complexes :

A very sharp band is seen in all the complexes around 3310 cm^{-1} due to NH stretch. The negative shift of the band by 150 cm^{-1} is an indication of co-ordination¹⁵. The NH deformation vibrations are seen in the region $1600\text{-}1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the free ligand. Co-ordination is known to cause a positive shift in these and hence in complexes, one sharp band is seen at 1605 cm^{-1} due to this mode. The NH bending models are also found to be shifted to higher frequency due to co-ordination and out of the three such vibrations the NH rocking is seen around 750 cm^{-1} . It is thus clear that the positions of all these bands suggest co-ordination of the ligand^{16,17}.

I. R. spectra of pyridine complexes :

The co-ordination of pyridine molecule to metals is known to cause a tightening of the aromatic ring and hence the important bands undergo positive shift¹⁸ some such bands which indicate co-ordination are as follows :

(a) Between $1430\text{-}1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, four bands are seen in free pyridine which are due to $\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and ring stretchings. The 1625 cm^{-1} and 1593 cm^{-1} bands of pyridine, which are combination bands ($60+12$ or $1+6b$) merge together and appear as a single band at 1635 cm^{-1} . The weak band at 1570 cm^{-1} of pyridine does not appear in the complex but the 1578 cm^{-1} band undergoes positive shift and occurs at 1600 cm^{-1} .

(b) The ring breathing models at 995 cm^{-1} shifts to 1010 cm^{-1} in complex, while the three $\text{C}-\text{H}$ deformations at 1217 cm^{-1} , 1145 cm^{-1} and 1068 cm^{-1} in free ligand appear in complex with positive shift at 1295 , 1158 and 1070 cm^{-1} ¹⁹.

From the above discussion it follows that complexes are tetra co-ordinated, two co-ordination positions are occupied by succinate ion and other two by amines. The complexes are all paramagnetic μ_{eff} lying in the range $1.845\text{-}1.921$ B.M. suggesting a planer geometry for complexes.

The diffuse reflectance spectra contain only one main but very broad band in the region $12.50\text{-}20 \text{ kK}$, the position of which depends upon the crystal field strength of amines, on theoretical considerations three bands are expected corresponding to the transitions ; in the planer geometry-

which in the present complexes are grouped together in one absorption envelope and appear in the form of a single very broad band^{20,21}. The position of this band however rules out the tetrahedral structures as the same are expected to give one band in the near I.R. region at 9.00 kK ²².

The position of this absorption band is equal to Dq , which thus comes out to be around 1250 cm^{-1} . It is, however, found that the Dq values obtained for the aniline and toluidine complexes are lower than the corresponding values for pyridine complexes, which is in agreement with positions of these amines in spectrochemical series.

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